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EPIGRAPHISCHE MITTEILUNGEN AUS ANTALYA VI

THE LAMP-STAND OFFERINGS OF PRIMIPILARIUS FLAVIUS BASSUS TO APOLLO PATROOS IN PATARA*

In 1994, the team responsible for archaeological excavations at Patara discovered the base depicted below. It was found around the eastern part of the ancient port on the southern side of the cape, some 200 metres from the theatre in the north-west. In 1996, the squeeze of the inscription on this base was made by S. Şahin while he was working in Patara on efforts to publish the inscriptions there. In 2000, the base was moved to the Museum of Antalya, where it has no inventory number.

The base has a triangular form. The edges of the upper part, which was meant to bear the offerings, are 0.38m; the middle section, with its inscription, is 0.40m; the bottom section is 0.45m. The base has four feet: three rectangular ones in the corners and a circular one in the centre. The inscription can be read in spite of the missing sections of the right half. H: 0.51 m; w: 0.425 m; th: 0.37 m; letters: 0.02 m.

* I thank my teachers, Prof. Dr. Fahri Işık (director of the excavations at Patara) and Prof. Dr. Sencer Şahin, who have allowed and advised me to publish this base and its inscription.

Φλαβίος Βάσσος
 [π]ρειμο[π]ειλά[ριο]ς,
 θεῷ ἐπη[κόω] Ἀπό]λ-
 λωνι Πατ[ρώφ] τὰς] λυ-
 χνίας σὺν [τοῖς] λυ-
 χνοῖς χαριστή[ριον]

Flavius Bassus,
Primipilarius, (offered)
to the listening god Apollo
Patroos (these) lamp-stands
with (their) lamps,
as a thanksgiving.

The important features for dating the inscription lie in the historical records of the temple of Apollo in Patara. There is no precise evidence for the location of the temple of Apollo, which was first mentioned by Herodotus¹, later by geographers such as Strabo², Mela³ and by many other authors. The inscription⁴ in which the grants donated by Opramoas of Rodiapolis following an earthquake (which took place in 142 AD), which damaged cities, can be taken into account for dating the base. In this long inscription, the oracle of Patara is mentioned in two different places. In one of them⁵, some money is given to revive the implementation of the god Apollo's word. The Flavian Period is the terminus post quem for the inscription; in the case of the nomen gentilicium, the owner is Flavius. However, the lamps must have been

¹ Herodotus I,182: καὶ κατὰ περ ἐν Πατάρουσι τῆς Λυκίης ἡ πρόμαντις τοῦ θεοῦ, ἐπεὶ γένηται· οὐ γὰρ ὧν αἰεὶ ἐστὶ χρηστήριον αὐτόθι· ἐπεὶ δὲ γένηται τότε ὧν συγκατακληῖται τὰς νύκτας ἕσω ἐν τῷ νηῷ.

² Strabo 14,3,6: μετὰ δὲ τὴν Ἑάνθον Πάταρα, καὶ αὕτη μεγάλη πόλις λιμένα ἔχουσα καὶ ἱερὸν Ἀπόλλωνος.

³ Mela 1,82: *illam nobilem facit delubrum Apollinis quondam opibus et oraculi{s} fide Delphico simile.*

⁴ TAM II 905 (see now C. Kokkinia, Die Opramoas-Inschrift von Rhodoapolis, Bonn 2000).

⁵ TAM II 905, XVII, 65.

an offering associated with a re-use of the temple. Also, the style of the lettering is typical of the 2nd half of the 2nd century. Architectural remains found in the place from where the base rolled down, such as columns, inscribed fragments of a rather large architrave and ceiling decorations, suggest that there must have been an important building in this area. One can naturally assume that these remains may belong to the temple of Apollo when it is taken into account that the base was also found in the same vicinity.

It has been concluded from the context of the inscription that Flavius Bassus offers a prayer relating to an unknown suffering and promises to offer lamp-stands with lamps, in order to rid himself of this suffering. Surely, Apollo hears (ἐπήκοος) his prayer and makes his wish come true. So, Flavius Bassus makes his vows come true as a measure of gratitude (χαριστήριον), a promise made by Bassus himself.

πρειμοπειλάριος (Lat. Primipilarius): Here we see the form of πρειμοπειλάριος, similar to the other πριμοπιλάριος or πριμοπιλάριος in the inscriptions.⁶ Flavius Bassus was in charge as a Primus Pilus in legion, in other words he was the first centurion of the first centurio of the first cohort of a legion. When a Primus Pilus finishes his office, he becomes a Primipilarius. A retired superior Primipilarii could be appointed to the imperial service.⁷

Only three individuals have been known to be Primipilarius from the province of Lycia and Pamphylia:

- 1) **Marcus Titianus of Balbura**⁸
- 2) **Lucius Gavius Fronto of Attaleia**⁹
- 3) **Bryonianus Lollianus of Side**¹⁰

These three returned to their respective native countries and took up some imperial or civil services after finishing their offices in the legion. In this way, Flavius Bassus also arrived in Patara and offered lamp-stands with their lamps, though we do not know precisely whether Patara was in fact his native country or not.

ἐπήκοος: Apollo was being worshipped as θεὸς ἐπήκοος meaning "the god hearing the prayers from above", together with the other gods/goddesses.¹¹

λυχνία: This word comes to mean "lamp-stand". Bassus offered these lamp-stands with their lamps, which is **λύχνος** in Greek. These lamps were made either of terra cotta, copper alloy, silver or gold. However, it is not clear what kind of material was used for the lamps of this base, since these have not been discovered.

⁶ For example see: the honourific inscriptions of Bryonianus Lollianus: J. Nollé, I. v. Side II, nos. 105–110: πρειμοπειλάριον. In an other (unpublished) foundation inscription found in Patara, which probably belongs to the 2nd century A.D., it appears as πρειμπειλάριον.

⁷ For general information, see: B. Dobson, *Die Primipilares*, Bonn 1978.

⁸ Dobson, op.cit., no. 116; M. Wörle, *Stadt und Fest im kaiserzeitlichen Kleinasien*, München 1988 (Vestigia 39), 63; IGR III, 472; IGR III, 576; IGR III, 500, col. III 28-31.

⁹ Dobson, op. cit., 115.

¹⁰ IGR III, 810 and 811; ZPE 26, 1977, 71-81; AE 1966, 471.

¹¹ For ἐπήκοος, see: O. Weinreich, *ΘΕΟΙ ΕΠΗΚΟΟΙ*, Athen. Mitt. 37, 1912, 1-68.

It is well known that lamp offerings were not only being made to Apollo. An example of this can be seen in the inscriptions on ceramic vessels found in Cyprus, which point to the lamps being offered to the nymphs.¹²

Also, in a dedication inscription found in Syria, a lamp-stand and a lamp were offered to the goddess Leukothea (...τὴν [λ]υχνίαν καὶ τὸν λύχνον ἀφιέρωσε τῇ Θεᾷ Λευκοθέα...) ¹³. A very similar example which is believed to have come from Afyon-Çavdarlıhisar in Phrygia¹⁴, shows that lamp-stands and lamps were offered to Apollo, by being inscribed with Μ.. 'Ερέννιος Ἐρμόλαος ὑπὲρ Ἄλκης τῆς θυγατρὸς εὐχὴν Ἀπόλλωνι τὰς λυχνίας σὺν τοῖς λύχνοις.¹⁵

χαριστήριον: This word includes the meanings of "thanking, thanksgiving etc." Also other expressions like εὐχαριστήριον, εὐχαριστέω appear in the inscriptions.¹⁶ This term is used frequently in Lycia and Pamphylia.¹⁷

Ἀπόλλων Πάτροος: The epithet of 'Patroos' used especially for Apollo means "of or from one's father, coming or inherited after him" or "as expressing *patrimonial possession*, from *πάτριος* as expressing hereditary manners, customs, institutions" according to Liddell – Scott. This expression comes to mean that Apollo is the native god of the region, takes a special place among the other gods and has a special cult in Lycia.¹⁸ Apollo, however, was also being worshipped with the epithet of 'Helios'.¹⁹

Flavius Bassus: It is not completed in the onomastic examination of the inscription. All the onomastic data show that the dating of the base is between the Flavian period and the first quarter of the third century.

Although triangular works like this base are not made in other cities of Lycia, Pamphylia, Pisidia and Cilicia as an offering to gods, there is one similar example²⁰, a grave stele from Kayadibi köyü near Arsada. However, in Greece and Italy triangular stands were prevalent.

The dedication of a τρίπους made of metal was a very old tradition. The tripods, which were one of the most valuable domestic items, were offered to the gods/goddesses.²¹ Offering of a τρίπους begun in the Geometric period. More than two hundred tripods of the 9th and

¹² SEG XXX (1980) no.1608; also for general information see: T.B. Mitford, *The Nymphaeum of Kafizin. The Inscribed Pottery*, Berlin 1980 (Kadmos suppl. II).

¹³ SEG XLIV (1994) no. 1326.

¹⁴ For this subject see: L. Robert, *Documents de l'Asie Mineure*, Paris 1987, 335-340.

¹⁵ SEG XXXII (1982), no. 1268; Robert, *op. cit.*, 340.

¹⁶ L. Robert, *Hellenica X*, 1955, 55; P. Hermann – E. Varinlioglu, *Theoi Pereudenoï*, EA 3, 1984, p.10 nr.5; p. 12 fn. 44; E. Varinlioglu, *Inscripfen von Stratonikeia in Karien*, EA 12, 1988, 84; TAM V 1, 455; T. Corsten, *I. v. Prusa ad Olympum I* (I.K. 39), 72 no. 48b1.

¹⁷ For example: TAM II 264 and 265 (Xanthus); SEG XXVI, nr.1438 (Oinoanda). In Pamphylia: SEG XVII, no.680 (Attaleia).

¹⁸ For the cult of Apollo in Patara and Apollon Patroos, see: P. Frei, *Die Götterkulte Lykiens in der Kaiserzeit*, ANRW II 18,3 (1990), 1757; M. Zimmermann, *Lykia I*, 1994, 109.

¹⁹ TAM II 403 (Patara).

²⁰ C. Naour, *Inscriptions de Lycie*, ZPE 24, 1977, 273 no. 4 and pl. IX,4.

²¹ E. Reisch, *Griechische Weihgeschenke*, Prag–Wien–Berlin (1890), 6; K. Schwendemann, *Der Dreifuß. Eine formen- und religionsgeschichtlicher Versuch*, JDAI 36, 1921, 98; H. Riemann, s.v. *Tripodes*, RE Suppl. 8 (1956), 869.

10th centuries B.C. were discovered in Olympia²²; triangular stands have also been found in the temple of Apollo Ptoion.²³

From the Classical period onwards, the tripod was used as a prize given in choregeias, which were theatrical shows. The best traditional tripods were located in Athens. Hundreds of bronze tripods, which had been dedicated to Dionysus as prizes of the choregeias, decorated the edges of the Tripous/tripod Street in Athens. These tripods also had a base, which was shaped like the base in Patara.²⁴ This tradition was kept alive until the late Roman period.²⁵ The bases, which were discovered in the theatre of Orchomenos in Boeotia and dedicated to Dionysus, are very similar to the base of Patara.²⁶ Triangular bases whose purpose was to carry statues²⁷ (rarely) or lamps are also in existence.²⁸ So, in the light of these examples, we can see that there were in existence bases with legs that carried lamps. These legs were probably tied together, giving them a tripod appearance.

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ÖZET

ANTALYA'DAN EPIGRAFI HABERLERİ VI: Primipilarius Flavius Bassus'un Patara'da Apollon Patroos'a sunduğu adak şamdanları

Altılık 1994 yılında Patara limanının doğu ağzında, tiyatronun 200 m kadar kuzeybatısına düşen burnun güney yamacında Patara kazı ekibi tarafından bulunmuştur. Altılıktaki önemli kısım üstünde bulunan dört adet metal oturtma delikleridir. Bu deliklerden dörtgen olan üç tanesi köşelerde, yuvarlak ve daha az derin olan dördüncüsü ise merkezde bulunmaktadır. Altılıktaki yazıtın, sağ yarısı kötü durumda olmasına rağmen tamamlayabilmek mümkün olmuştur:

"Primipilarius Flavius Bassus, duaları işiten tanrı Apollon Patroos için, (bu) kandil altılıklarını kandilleriyle beraber bir şükran adığı olarak (adadı)".

Yazıtın tarihlenmesi için Patara Apollon Tapınağı tarihçesi göz önüne alınmıştır. Her ne kadar Flavius soy adıyla I yy. özelliği gösterse de, Rhodiapolisli Opramoas'ın yapmış olduğu yardımlarla tapınağın yeniden işlemeye başladığı tarihten sonra ve *Constitutio Antoniniana*'dan (212) önce olmalıdır. Flavius Bassus lejyonda *primus pilus* olarak görev yapmış, bu görevi bitikten (primipilarius) sonraki bir dönemde Patara'da Apollon Patroos'tan bir temennide bulunmuştur. Bunun gerçekleşmesi sonucunda ise kandil altılıkları ile kandiller adanmış ve bunu yakın çevrede görülmeeyen bir biçimde, bir üçayak formunda yapmıştır.

²² M. Maaß, *Olympische Forschungen* 10, Berlin 1978, 117.; P.C. Pol, *Antike Bronzetechnik. Kunst und Handwerk antiker Erzbildner*, München (1985), 30.

²³ P. Guillon, *Les Trepieds du Ptoion I*, Paris 1943, 23., no. XXII; J. Ducat, *Les Kouroi du Ptoion. Le Sanctuaire d'Apollon Ptoieus a l'époque archaïque*, Paris 1971, 401 no. 251 and pl. 138.

²⁴ H. Jung, *Die Reliefbasis Athen, National Museum 1463: Spätklassisch oder neuattisch?*, *MarbWpr* 1986, 3-38, pl. 1-3.

²⁵ Reisch, *op.cit.*, 91; M. Jacob-Felsch, *Die Entwicklung der griechischen Statuenbasen und die Aufstellung der Statuen*, *Waldsassen* 1969, 98; E. Stikas, "Τριπλευρα κοινόκρανα κορυφώματα και μνημεία", *Archaiologiki Ephimeris*, 1961, 159-179.

²⁶ P. Amandry – T. Spyropoulos, *Monuments chorégiques d'Orchomène de Béotie*, *BCH* 98, 1974, 171-246.

²⁷ For examples: Stikas, *op.cit.*; Jacob-Felsch, *op.cit.*, 56.

²⁸ H-U. Cain, *Römische Marmorkandelaber*, Mainz 1985 (see the part of catalogue).